

Performance of 1980 transplanted aman rice in 12 selected thana of Bangladesh

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A large-scale yield assessment study of the 1980 Bangladesh transplanted (t) aman rice crop was undertaken in 12 thana under 6 districts to determine the relative performance of new high yielding varieties (HYV), Pajam (an intermediate type between HYV and local varieties and known as Mashuri in other countries), and local varieties. A crop-cut of 5-m² area was harvested and the grain yield was adjusted to 14% moisture content. A total of 453 crop-cuts were analyzed for this report. Yields of the 1980 t. aman crop were high, HYV t. aman (BR4, BR3, IR5, IR20) gave quantitatively higher yields than Pajam except in Boda thana of Dinajpur district (see figure). The performance of the local t. aman varieties was inferior to that of HYV and Pajam in all thana, except at Sherpur where the local t. aman gave a slightly higher grain yield than Pajam. On the basis of 453 sample crop-cuts, the average grain yields for HYV, Pajam, and local t. aman were 4.5, 3.9, and 3.1 t/ha. Thus, our results indicated that under current farmer management, the HYV t. aman could produce additional grain yields of 593

Yields of three groups of transplanted aman rice varieties in 12 thana of Bangladesh in 1980.

and 1,470 kg/ha in Bangladesh if grown instead of Pajam and local varieties. The study also indicated that constraints in

Khulna and Patuakhali districts limit the grain yield of t. aman rice and particularly of the modern varieties. ■

Agroeconomic evaluation of farmers' direct-seeded upland rice crop at a rainfed site in Bangladesh

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Agroeconomic monitoring of the farmers' rainfed aus rice crop was done

at the BRRI cropping systems research site at Alimganj, Rajshahi district, during 1980. Traditionally, farmers at this site grow local varieties of aus rice in aus rice - transplanted aman rice, aus rice - rabi (winter) crops, and aus rice - t. aman rice - rabi crops patterns. Four modern rice varieties were introduced at the site in 1980 to compare their performance with the traditional local varieties under farmers' management.

All varieties were seeded between 10 and 17 May. Seeds were broadcast for

all local and most of the modern variety fields. All farmers used fertilizers and hand weeding. Except for Purbachi, the average fertilizer rates for the modern varieties were higher (see table) than for the local varieties. Weeds were a problem in all fields and farmers hand weeded 2 to 5 times. Insecticide was used only on the modern varieties. The average field duration of local varieties ranged between 86 and 89 days; that of the modern varieties ranged from 100 to 138 days. The local varieties Hashikalmi

Management practices, productivity, and costs and returns analysis of farmers' direct-seeded rainfed aus rice at Alimganj cropping systems research site, Rajshahi district, Bangladesh, 1980.

Observation	Local variety		Modern variety ^a			
	Hashikalmi	Dharial	BR1	BR3	BR9	Purbachi
Sample number	6	4	3	2	4	1
Seeding date range	10-17 May	13-17 May	10-13 May	10-13 May	10-17 May	10 May
Av N-P ₂ O ₅ -K ₂ O rate (kg/ha)	34-44-40	41-38-30	92-43-19	64-49-39	72-54-33	42-56-0
Hand weeding frequency (range)	2-4	2-3	3-5	3-5	3-5	2
Farmers (%) who used insecticide	0	0	33	100	50	100
Av field days	89	86	113	138	115	100
Av grain yield (t/ha)	2.28	2.19	2.85	3.20	2.23	2.48
Grain yield (kg/day per ha)	25.62	25.49	25.19	23.15	19.36	24.77
Grain yield range (t/ha)	1.9-3.0	1.8-2.8	2.4-3.3	3.0-3.4	2.1-2.3	—
Av production costs (US\$/ha) ^b	146	155	234	218	187	176
Production costs range (US\$/ha)	119-217	143-172	187-296	180-257	188-220	—
Av net return (US\$/ha)	313	256	348	435	268	290
Net return range (US\$/ha)	164-403	189-369	291-453	428-442	247-303	—
Benefit-cost ratio	3.14	2.65	2.48	2.99	2.44	2.64

^aFirst introduced at the site. ^bExchange rate used in computation: US\$1 = Taka 15.

and Dharial yielded 2.28 and 2.19 t/ha, respectively. The modern varieties produced about 9 to 40% higher average yield than the better local variety Hashikalmi. However, both the local varieties gave higher daily production per hectare. On the average, the production

cost for modern varieties was 35% higher than for the local varieties. Hashikalmi gave the highest benefit-cost ratio (3.14) and BR9 gave the lowest, apparently because of heat injury at the reproductive stage. Results of the present monitoring study indicated that

although BR1 and BR3 have prospects in the area, it might be advantageous to continue the use of local aus varieties until higher yielding and earlier modern varieties are identified or developed for the agroclimatic conditions at the site. ■

ERRATA

In vol. 6, no. 2 (Apr 1981) Genetic evaluation and utilization — overall progress, page 3 item: RAU21-168-1-2, a promising rice variety for water-logged areas of Bihar, India, paragraph 3 should read:

The tall-statured RAU21-168-1-2 matures in 150-155 days in the field

and is moderately resistant to bacterial blight. It has short bold grains and is weakly sensitive to photoperiod.

In vol. 6, no. 3 (Jun 1981) Soil and Crop Management, page 22, item: Population of the weed *Marsilea quadrifolia* in plots with azolla. The

name of the weed was misspelled in title and in article. *Panicum colonum* and *Echinochloa colona* are the same weed. *Pistia stratiotes* is the correct spelling. *Cyperus rotundus* is not a wetland weed.